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Sources, levels, and determinants of indoor air pollutants in Europe: a systematic review

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Abstract:	Clean air is a requirement for life, and the quality of indoor air is a health determinant since people spend most of their daily time indoors. The aim of this study was to systematically review the available evidence regarding the sources, determinants and concentrations of indoor air pollutants in a set of scenarios under study in K-HEALTHinAIR project. To this end, a systematic review was performed to review the

	<p>available studies published between the years 2013-2023, for several settings (schools, homes, hospitals, lecture halls, retirement homes, public transports and canteens), where sources and determinants of the indoor pollutants concentrations was assessed. After a two-stage screening in abstract and full-text, 148 papers were included for data extraction. For particulate matter, carbon dioxide and volatile organic compounds, several emission sources were identified (occupancy, human activities, resuspension, cleaning products, disinfectants, craft activities, cooking, smoking), with ventilation, number of occupants, building characteristics, being considered as important determinants. This review made also possible to discuss some of the actions that are already in place or should be implemented in the future to prevent and control the presence of pollutants indoors.</p>
Opposed Reviewers:	

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Dear Editors-in-Chief,

Herewith I enclose the manuscript entitled: **“Sources, levels, and determinants of indoor air pollutants in Europe: a systematic review”** for publication in Science of the Total Environment.

The present work reviewed the scientific evidence made available in the last decade in Europe in what regards the sources and determinants of indoor air quality. It approaches this topic in the perspective of gathering information to support the development of the activities of a Horizon Europe funded project, the K-HEALTHinAIR (www.k-healthinair.eu/). To accomplish this, a multidisciplinary team of co-authors was assembled to ensure different views for the review of papers. In this review, 148 papers were reviewed comprising several indoor scenarios: schools, homes, lecture halls, retirement homes, hospitals, canteens and public transport.

Globally, this manuscript represents an important tool for policymakers, since it gathers data about the sources and determinants of the presence of indoor air pollutants, thus filling some gaps in a relatively understudied area and supporting new indoor air quality policies.

I really appreciate that you could consider this manuscript to publish in Science of the Total Environment.

Yours faithfully,

Carla Martins

Sources, levels, and determinants of indoor air pollutants in Europe: a systematic review

Highlights

- Sources and determinants of indoor air quality in Europe were reviewed.
- Sources identified were occupancy, human activity, cleaning products.
- Determinants identified were ventilation, type of building and number of occupants.
- This review supports the development of new policies and standards.

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1 **Sources, levels, and determinants of indoor air pollutants in Europe: a**
2 **systematic review**

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29

30 **Abstract**

31 Clean air is a requirement for life, and the quality of indoor air is a health determinant
32 since people spend most of their daily time indoors. The aim of this study was to
33 systematically review the available evidence regarding the sources, determinants and
34 concentrations of indoor air pollutants in a set of scenarios under study in K-
35 HEALTHinAIR project. To this end, a systematic review was performed to review the
36 available studies published between the years 2013-2023, for several settings (schools,
37 homes, hospitals, lecture halls, retirement homes, public transports and canteens),
38 where sources and determinants of the indoor pollutants concentrations was assessed.
39 After a two-stage screening in abstract and full-text, 148 papers were included for data
40 extraction. For particulate matter, carbon dioxide and volatile organic compounds,
41 several emission sources were identified (occupancy, human activities, resuspension,
42 cleaning products, disinfectants, craft activities, cooking, smoking), with ventilation,
43 number of occupants, building characteristics, being considered as important
44 determinants. This review made also possible to discuss some of the actions that are
45 already in place or should be implemented in the future to prevent and control the
46 presence of pollutants indoors.

47

48 **1. Introduction**

49 In high income countries, people spend 80 to 90% of their time in indoor settings
50 performing activities of daily living, working, and sleeping, where the presence of
51 pollutants is a concern (Carslaw et al., 2024). Nevertheless, indoor air quality remains
52 relatively understudied, thus contributing for standards and regulatory gaps (Morawska
53 et al., 2024). Many factors contribute to poor indoor air quality (IAQ) and pollutants can
54 have their origin on the outdoor pollution, as well as sources that are unique to the indoor
55 environment such as (i) human activities (e.g., smoking, burning solid fuels, cooking, and
56 cleaning); (ii) emissions from building and construction materials, and furniture and, also,
57 (iii) biological contaminants, such as fungi, bacteria and viruses mainly due to occupancy

58 (WHO, 2010). In the meantime, knowing the key determinants and pollution sources is
59 extremely relevant to define the best risk management approaches at the technical and
60 policy levels (Chojer et al., 2024). In the last years, country members of the European
61 Union had made an effort to fill the gaps in the area of indoor air quality, not only through
62 policies but by funding research projects as well (European Commission, 2024).
63 The aim of this study was to systematically review the available evidence regarding the
64 sources, determinants and concentrations of indoor air pollutants in a set of scenarios
65 under study in K-HEALTHinAIR project.

66

67 **2. Methods**

68 The literature review was performed based on the Prisma Methodology (Shamseer et
69 al., 2015), about sources, determinants of indoor air pollutants presence and
70 concentrations of these pollutants in the European region for the period 2013-2023. The
71 search string considered three main groups: the topic, the pollutants, and the settings
72 (Figure S1).

73 The search was performed on 7 June 2023, and the search string used was: (("indoor
74 air" OR "indoor air pollution" OR "indoor air quality") AND ("VOC" OR "particulate matter"
75 OR "formaldehyde" OR "carbon dioxide" OR "nitrogen oxides" OR "ozone" OR "radon")
76 AND ("hospital" OR "public transport" OR "market" OR "canteen" OR "residence" OR
77 "lecture hall" OR "home" OR "school")). Three peer-reviewed literature databases were
78 searched: (i) Pubmed (all-fields and relevant MeSH terms); (ii) Scopus (only title-
79 abstract-keywords: excludes conference papers, notes, editorials, and letters, etc.) and
80 (iii) Web of Science (core collection only; excludes proceeding papers, meeting
81 abstracts, news items, editorial material, and letters).

82 The inclusion criteria were: i) English language; ii) study reporting primary data; iii)
83 timeframe 2013-2023; iv) studies developed in a European context. Grey literature
84 sources were not considered. The references were collected, managed, deduplicated,
85 and screened using Mendeley and Microsoft Excel software.

86

87 **2.1. First Stage Screening**

88 Relevance screening of the publications identified in the literature search was performed.

89 The titles and abstracts were screened by two independent reviewers per reference with

90 a third reviewer to resolve conflicts. References were excluded when two reviewers

91 agreed on the exclusion. For the first stage, four questions were used sequentially to

92 screen and select papers for further stages, summarized in the decision tree (Figure 1):

93 (Q1) Does it report primary data? (yes or maybe – include; no – exclude); (Q2) Does it

94 report data for indoor air pollution? (yes or maybe – include; no – exclude); (Q3) Does it

95 concern any of the following scenarios: hospital, nursing homes, metro station, market,

96 canteens, student residence, lecture hall, homes, schools (primary and secondary

97 schools)? (yes or maybe – include; no – exclude); (Q4) Was the study developed in a

98 European country? (yes or maybe – include; no – exclude). References that fulfilled the

99 inclusion criteria proceeded to full text screening, i.e., the second stage of screening.

100

101 **2.2. Second Stage Screening**

102 In the second stage, each complete paper (i.e., full-text) was examined by one reviewer,

103 based on five questions, summarized in the decision tree (Figure 1): Q4: Was the study

104 developed in a European country? (yes – include; no – exclude); Q5: Is it an

105 epidemiological study? (yes – include; no – exclude); Q6: Does it report levels of

106 pollutants? (yes – include; no – exclude); Q7: Does it identify sources of exposure? (yes

107 – include; no – exclude); Q8: Does it identify determinants of exposure? (yes – include;

108 no – exclude). Question Q4 was repeated since only studies developed in Europe were

109 considered for this systematic review and this information frequently is not available in

110 title and abstract. Questions Q4 and Q5 were used sequentially to exclude papers, and

111 questions Q7 and Q8 were considered in pairs with Q6, i.e., one of the pairs Q6-Q7 or

112 Q6-Q8 should had two answers “YES” to considered for data extraction. For this study,

113 we considered determinants of the presence of IAQ pollutants as they are described in

114 the paper by Koivisto et al. (2021) with adaptations to the IAQ context. Hence, the
 115 following were considered determinants: i) the presence of emission sources (e.g.,
 116 furniture, cooking processes, cleaning operations, outdoor air); ii) ventilation conditions
 117 that can influence dilution and removal of pollutants iii) occupants' behaviour such as
 118 smoking, using footwear indoors inside (Koivisto et al., 2021).
 119

120

121

Figure 1 - Decision tree for stage I screening (a) and stage II screening (b).

122

123

124 **2.3. Data extraction and analysis of sources and determinants of** 125 **exposure**

126 At a final stage, data were extracted considering several aspects of each paper related
 127 with setting characteristics, study design, pollutants, sources, and determinants
 128 identified as such. A narrative synthesis of the review findings was generated

129 qualitatively comparing the results of all studies for sources and determinants, organized
130 by each setting and pollutant.

131

132 3. Results

133

134 3.1. Overview of the studies

135 The literature search yielded a total of 4370 papers among the three databases used
136 (Scopus, Web of Science, and Pubmed) with a total of 1478 records examined at stage
137 I and 703 records screened at stage II. Figure 2 shows an overview of the papers
138 obtained at each stage and the exclusion workflow.

139

140

141 Figure 2 - Workflow and results for stage I and stage II of the systematic literature review.

142

143 In stage II, 555 papers were excluded due to several reasons: studies developed outside
144 Europe (n=335); studies developed under experimental and/or laboratorial conditions
145 (n=119); and for not reporting levels of indoor pollutants and not identifying sources or
146 determinants as such (n=101). Therefore, 148 papers were eligible for data extraction

147 and analysis. Figure 3 describes the number of scenarios studied in screened papers.
148 Schools were the most studied (n=73, 45%), followed by homes (n=59, 37%). The least
149 explored scenarios were the lecture halls (n=9, 6%), hospitals (n=8, 5%), retirement
150 homes (n=5, 3%), transportation (n=5, 3%) and canteens (n=1, 1%).

151

152 Figure 3 - Scenarios studied in the scientific literature eligible for data extraction.

153

154 Overall, the selected studies presented different study designs, with cross-sectional
155 studies being the most frequently reported (n=129), followed by cohort studies (n=9) and
156 case-control studies (n=10). Regarding analysis of results, 27/73 studies in schools,
157 27/59 studies in schools, and 3/8 studies in hospitals, performed a statistical analysis to
158 establish an association between sources and pollutants and to identify the determinants
159 of indoor concentrations. Statistical methods for source and determinant attribution
160 ranged from inferential tests such as Mann-Whitney, Kruskal-Wallis, ANOVA, to more
161 complex analysis using Principal Component Analysis, linear mixed effects and
162 multivariate regression models.

163

164 3.2. Schools

165 Eligible studies for data extraction focused on primary and secondary schools, thus
166 revealing the potential exposure of children from 6 to 18 years, teachers, and other
167 support staff. Sources and determinants of indoor air pollutants are described in the
168 Table 1.

169 For carbon dioxide (CO₂), most of the studies identified occupancy as the main source,
170 with the number of people being a determinant factor for indoor CO₂ levels (Cabovská et
171 al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2014; Hänninen et al., 2017; Kaewrat et al., 2021; Lazovic
172 et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016c; Muhič and Muhič, 2022; Sá
173 et al., 2017; Schibuola and Tambani, 2020; Stabile et al., 2016; Turanjanin et al., 2014;
174 Ukëhaxhaj et al., 2023; Vornanen-Winqvist et al., 2018a, 2018b). The outdoor
175 environment was also identified as a source, highlighting the influence of outdoor air on
176 indoor air quality (Lazovic et al., 2016). Regarding determinants of the presence of indoor
177 pollutants, the type of ventilation (Jovanović et al., 2014; Kovacevic et al., 2015; Lazovic
178 et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016; Mečiarová et al., 2018; Sá et al., 2017; Turanjanin et
179 al., 2014; Villanueva et al., 2021; Vornanen-Winqvist et al., 2018a), classroom volume
180 (Madureira et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016c), building maintenance (Stabile et al.,
181 2016), classroom orientation (Turanjanin et al., 2014), or physical activities (Lazovic et
182 al., 2016), were also considered important factors with influence on indoors CO₂ levels.

183 The most recent analytical techniques have made it possible to quantify different Volatile
184 Organic Compounds (VOCs). Nevertheless, total VOCs are still the most frequently used
185 parameter in indoor air quality studies. The most relevant sources identified for the
186 presence of VOCs' in schools are cleaning products and materials used for students'
187 activities (e.g., crafts, paints, glues) (Madureira et al., 2016; Mečiarová et al., 2018;
188 Nicole Ninyà et al., 2022; Sá et al., 2017). Furniture, floors, and textiles were also
189 recognized as possible sources of VOCs (Fromme et al., 2013; Madureira et al., 2016;
190 Madureira et al., 2016c). Contribution from outdoor sources were also identified for
191 benzene (de Gennaro et al., 2013; Madureira et al., 2016; Marzocca et al., 2017;

192 Szabados et al., 2021; Ukėhaxhaj et al., 2023), toluene, ethylbenzene and xylenes
193 (Marzocca et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021), and styrene (Marzocca et al., 2017). The
194 importance of good planning and installation of mechanical ventilation systems must be
195 stressed to avoid the transport of pollutants from outdoor or other indoor locations. These
196 systems should have a periodic maintenance plan to prevent them from becoming a
197 potential source of exposure. Several factors were identified as determinants of indoor
198 VOCs levels, with ventilation conditions being one of the most frequent (Fromme et al.,
199 2013; Jovanović et al., 2014; Madureira et al., 2016; Mečiarová et al., 2018). The number
200 of occupants (Madureira et al., 2016c), type of floor materials (Madureira et al., 2016),
201 or location in the building (Ukėhaxhaj et al., 2023) were also recognized as determinants.
202 There were some VOCs quantified in schools for which it was not possible to identify the
203 main sources (hexanal, propionaldehyde, acetaldehyde) highlighting the need for further
204 research dedicated to understanding the presence of these compounds indoors.
205 Formaldehyde is considered a VOC of particular concern, due to its common presence
206 in indoor environments, its high levels and toxicity (Jiang et al., 2018). From the studies
207 analysed the main sources of formaldehyde identified in schools were furniture and
208 wood-based materials (Brdarić et al., 2019; Jovanović et al., 2014; Sá et al., 2017),
209 textiles (Jovanović et al., 2014), electronic equipment (Brdarić et al., 2019), smoking (Hu
210 et al., 2022), and presence of molds/moisture (Brdarić et al., 2019). Following the same
211 pattern of other VOCs, ventilation conditions and type of ventilation (e.g., natural or
212 mechanical) were determinants of indoor formaldehyde levels (Brdarić et al., 2019;
213 Cabovská et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022; Jovanović et al., 2014; Sá et al., 2017), as well
214 as building characteristics (e.g., type of floor, location, and year of construction)
215 (Jovanović et al., 2014; Ukėhaxhaj et al., 2023).
216 Although some indoor sources such as wall materials and heating systems by
217 combustion were identified for nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), the outdoor sources are the major
218 contributors (i.e., outdoor air and traffic) and identified in more articles as such
219 (Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2015; Hu et al., 2022; Szabados et al., 2021;

220 Ukëhaxhaj et al., 2023; Villanueva et al., 2018). Regarding the factors that may influence
221 the indoor levels, the type of ventilation (Brdarić et al., 2019; Cabovská et al., 2022;
222 Jovanović et al., 2014), the number of occupants (Villanueva et al., 2018), and aspects
223 related to building characteristics (e.g., year of construction, location, floor level)
224 (Chatzidiakou et al., 2014; Ukëhaxhaj et al., 2023) were identified as determinants of the
225 presence of NO₂ in schools.

226 Most studies assessed the presence of 10 µm and 2.5 µm particulate matter (PM₁₀ and
227 PM_{2.5}, respectively), although three studies quantified 1.0 µm particles (Pacitto et al.,
228 2018; Polednik, 2013; Sá et al., 2017) and seven studies quantified 0.1 µm particles
229 (ultrafine particles) (Cavaleiro Rufo et al., 2016; Paunescu et al., 2017; Reche et al.,
230 2014; Rivas et al., 2014; Klara Slezakova et al., 2019; Villanueva et al., 2021). The
231 outdoor environment, mainly air pollution (schools located in heavy traffic areas), was
232 identified as contributing factor to indoor levels of PM₁₀ (Almeida et al., 2016; Alves et
233 al., 2016; Kovacevic et al., 2015; Pacitto et al., 2018; Pallarés et al., 2021; Polednik,
234 2013; Villanueva et al., 2021), PM_{2.5} (Alves et al., 2016; Amato et al., 2014; Kovacevic
235 et al., 2015; Polednik, 2013; Szabados et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2021), PM_{1.0} (Pacitto
236 et al., 2018) and PM_{0.1} (Cavaleiro Rufo et al., 2016; Reche et al., 2014; Slezakova et al.,
237 2019; Villanueva et al., 2021). The presence of students in school classrooms was also
238 a source of contamination, just as the number of people was noted as a determinant
239 (Almeida et al., 2016; Alves et al., 2016; Bamparesos et al., 2020; Cabovská et al.,
240 2022; Carballo et al., 2021; Di Gilio et al., 2017; Faria et al., 2020; Fischer et al., 2015;
241 Jovanović et al., 2014; Kovacevic et al., 2015; Polednik, 2013; Schibuola and Tambani,
242 2020). This is also related to times of students' activities, movements inside the
243 classrooms and cleaning at the end of the day, which several studies highlighted to
244 contribute to increase indoor levels of particulate matter. A very characteristic aspect of
245 school settings is the use of chalk, and this was noted in several studies as a source of
246 indoor particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM_{1.0} and PM_{0.1}) (Amato et al., 2014; Faria et al.,
247 2020; Pacitto et al., 2018; Polednik, 2013; Rivas et al., 2014; Sá et al., 2017; Slezakova

248 et al., 2019). Following the pattern of other indoor pollutants, ventilation plays a
249 significant role in the indoor particles levels, being identified as a determinant for all
250 particles size (Alves et al., 2016; Barmparesos et al., 2020; Cabovská et al., 2022;
251 Carballo et al., 2021; Chatzidiakou et al., 2014; Fischer et al., 2015; Jovanović et al.,
252 2014; Kovacevic et al., 2015; Madureira et al., 2016c; Polednik, 2013; Reche et al., 2014;
253 Slezakova et al., 2019; Stamp et al., 2020; Tofful and Perrino, 2015; Villanueva et al.,
254 2021; Vornanen-Winqvist et al., 2018a). Several aspects related to the building
255 characteristics were also identified as potential determinants: the floor level (Cavaleiro
256 Rufo et al., 2016; Slezakova et al., 2022), the construction materials (walls, windows)
257 (Polednik, 2013; Tofful and Perrino, 2015), type of playground (Amato et al., 2014), or
258 room orientation (influenced also by outdoor air pollution levels) (Amato et al., 2014;
259 Reche et al., 2014). An important contribution was the study that assessed the
260 differences in indoor particulate matter levels between schools where students wear
261 socks and schools where students kept their shoes inside (Leppänen et al., 2020). This
262 study showed that there is a significant difference in indoor PM₁₀ levels and that schools
263 where students wear socks presented lower levels of PM₁₀. This information is relevant
264 for the development of future mitigation measures.

265 Few studies quantified the presence of carbon monoxide (CO) in school facilities;
266 nevertheless, several sources were identified such as combustion systems for heating
267 (Hänninen et al., 2017), smoking (in secondary school) (Alves et al., 2016), and outdoor
268 sources (Sá et al., 2017). Ventilation and season were identified as the main
269 determinants of the presence of CO in schools (Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Sá et al.,
270 2017).

271 The geological origin of radon is well known and described in literature, and therefore,
272 the main sources described in schools were related to outdoor sources (e.g., soil and
273 nearby mining activities, granitic formations on the soil) (Azara et al., 2018; Branco et al.,
274 2016; Curado et al., 2020; Gulan et al., 2023; Madureira et al., 2016b). Since it is difficult
275 to eliminate the sources, it is essential to invest in reducing indoor contamination by

276 defining adequate characteristics for buildings, particularly for schools. Ventilation
277 (Branco et al., 2016; Curado et al., 2020; Gulan et al., 2023), construction materials
278 (Azara et al., 2018; Curguz et al., 2020), room volume and building location (Curado et
279 al., 2020; Madureira et al., 2016b), were also determining of indoor radon levels in the
280 schools studied. The number of occupants could lead to a higher need to use natural
281 ventilation and indirectly influence indoor radon levels.

282 For ozone (O₃), the outdoor environment was the only source of indoor levels mentioned
283 (Cabovská et al., 2022; Jovanović et al., 2014). Ventilation and the classroom location in
284 the building play a key role (south-facing windows and facing the street with higher
285 levels) (B Cabovská et al., 2022; Jovanović et al., 2014; Sá et al., 2017).

286 Exceeding available national legislation and recommendations (health-based guidelines)
287 was not reported in most of the studies. Nevertheless, and considering the availability of
288 legislation and recommendations in some countries, exceedance was reported in some
289 studies: Portugal (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, radon) (Faria et al., 2020; Madureira et al., 2016b;
290 Sá et al., 2017), Serbia (formaldehyde) (Jovanović et al., 2014), Poland (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀)
291 (Polednik, 2013; Polednik, 2013) and Malta (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) (Fsadni et al., 2018).

Table 1 – Sources, concentrations, and determinants of indoor air pollutants presence in schools.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources of exposure	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants of exposure	References
CO ₂	Occupancy Outdoor air	410 – 3780 ppm	1000-4434 ppm	Yes 11/26 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Room volume Season Building maintenance Classroom orientation Physical activities Other indoor pollutants	(Alves et al., 2016; Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2014; Hänninen et al., 2017; Jovanović et al., 2014; Kaewrat et al., 2021; Lazovic et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016; Madureira, Paciência, Rufo, Severo, et al., 2016; Mečiarová et al., 2018; Muhič & Muhič, 2022; Rufo et al., 2016; Sá et al., 2017; Schibuola & Tambani, 2020; Stabile et al., 2016; Turanjanin et al., 2014; Ukéhaxhaj et al., 2023; Villanueva et al., 2021; Vornanen-Winqvist, Järvi, et al., 2018; Vornanen-Winqvist, Salonen, et al., 2018)
Total VOC	Cleaning products Floor material Class materials (art & crafts, textiles) Consumer products	19-1543 µg/m ³	84-820.2 µg/m ³	No	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Season Room volume Type of floor	(Alves et al., 2016; Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Fromme et al., 2013; Jovanović et al., 2014; Madureira et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016c; Mečiarová et al., 2018; Ninyà et al., 2022; Sá et al., 2017)
Benzene	Outdoor environment Floor material Class materials (textiles)	0.44 – 5.24 µg/m ³	0.6 – 20.1 µg/m ³	Not reported	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation	(Brdarić et al., 2019; de Gennaro et al., 2013; Fromme et al., 2013; Madureira et al., 2016; Marzocca et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021; Ukéhaxhaj et al., 2023)
Limonene	Cleaning products Whiteboard Class activities Class materials (textiles) Other indoor sources	3.08 – 26.6 µg/m ³	3.6 – 249 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical)	(de Gennaro et al., 2013; Fromme et al., 2013; Marzocca et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020; Szabados et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2018)
Pinene	Cleaning products Class materials (textiles) Class activities	4.85 – 55.6 µg/m ³	9.9 – 73 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical)	(de Gennaro et al., 2013; Fromme et al., 2013; Stamp

	Other indoor sources					et al., 2020; Szabados et al., 2021)
Toluene	Outdoor environment Class materials (art & crafts, textiles) Other indoor sources	1.5 – 25 µg/m ³	1.9 – 202.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical)	(Fromme et al., 2013; Madureira et al., 2016; Marzocca et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021)
Naphtalene Tetrachloroethylene Trichloroethylene	Class materials (textiles)	0.5 – 2.18 µg/m ³ 0.09 – 4.4 µg/m ³ 0.19 – 0.45 µg/m ³	1 – 6.05 µg/m ³ 0.6 – 67.1 µg/m ³ NR	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical)	(Fromme et al., 2013)
Ethylbenzene Styrene Xylenes	Outdoor environment Class materials (art & crafts) Cleaning products	0.76 – 1.64 µg/m ³ 0.44 – 1.75 µg/m ³ 5.37 µg/m ³	1.4 – 9.14 µg/m ³ 0.43 – 4.2 µg/m ³ 34.6 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(Marzocca et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021)
Acetaldehyde Hexanal Propionaldehyde	Other indoor sources	5.28 – 9.31 µg/m ³ 9.17 – 15.8 µg/m ³ 1.49 µg/m ³	11 µg/m ³ 26.9 – 32.7 µg/m ³ 6.54 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(Szabados et al., 2021)
Decane	Furniture	NR	5.86 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(de Gennaro et al., 2013)
2-butoxyethanol	Cleaning products	31.5 µg/m ³	46.4 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(Marzocca et al., 2017)
Formaldehyde	Furniture (wood-based) Organic sources (dampness, mold) Electronics Class activities Smoking Traffic Class materials (textiles) Other indoor sources	0.01 – 102 µg/m ³	12.9 – 126.9 µg/m ³	Yes 1/7 studies	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Building' characteristics (location, age) Type of floor	(Brdarić et al., 2019; Blanka Cabovská et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022; Jovanović et al., 2014; Sá et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021; Ukéhaxhaj et al., 2023)
NO ₂	Outdoor environment Traffic Wall material Heating/combustion	4.89 – 31 µg/m ³	13.7 – 69 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation Number of occupants Floor level Building' characteristics (location, age)	(Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2015; Hu et al., 2022; Szabados et al., 2021; Ukéhaxhaj et al., 2023; Villanueva et al., 2018)
PM _{0.1}	Outdoor environment Traffic Resuspension Other indoor sources Chalk Cooking	2445-19241 part/cm ³	3985-185000 part/cm ³	Not reported	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Number of occupants Building' characteristics (location) Type of board	(Cavaleiro Rufo et al., 2016; Paunescu et al., 2017; Reche et al., 2014; Rivas et al., 2014; Klara Slezakova et al., 2019; Villanueva et al., 2021)

	Wood Other indoor sources				Floor level Type of floor Building with kitchen Room volume Time (period of day)	
PM _{1.0}	Chalk Traffic Occupancy Outdoor environment	2.4 – 70.1 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not reported	Building location Ventilation Number of occupants	(Pacitto et al., 2018; Polednik, 2013; Sá et al., 2017)
PM _{2.5}	Occupancy Chalk Outdoor air Resuspension (cleaning activities and movements of students) Traffic Soil Construction material Class materials (art & crafts, textiles) Organic sources (dampness, mold)	1.27 – 117 µg/m ³	27.1 – 279 µg/m ³	Yes 6/18 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation Building' characteristics (location) Type of playground Season Construction material Floor level Window's material	(Alves et al., 2016; Amato et al., 2014; Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2015; Di Gilio et al., 2017; Faria et al., 2020; Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Jovanović et al., 2014; Kovacevic et al., 2015; Pacitto et al., 2018; Polednik, 2013; Rivas et al., 2015, 2014; Sá et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020; Tofful and Perrino, 2015; Villanueva et al., 2021; Vormanen-Winqvist et al., 2018a)
PM ₁₀	Occupancy Chalk Resuspension (cleaning activities and movements of students) Outdoor air Soil Other indoor sources Organic sources (dampness, mold) Construction material Craft activities Traffic	14 – 388 µg/m ³	20 – 490 µg/m ³	Yes 7/21 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation Building' characteristics (location) Class activities Floor level Season Footwear (shoes/socks)	(Almeida et al., 2016; Alves et al., 2016; Bamparesos et al., 2020; Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2014; Faria et al., 2020; Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Fischer et al., 2015; Fromme et al., 2013; Jovanović et al., 2014; Kovacevic et al., 2015; Leppänen et al., 2020; Madureira et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016c; Pacitto et al., 2018; Pallarés et al., 2021; Polednik, 2013; Sá et al., 2017; Schibuola and Tambani, 2020; Szabados et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2021)
CO	Outdoor environment Smoking Combustion	0.42 – 9.1 ppm 0.48 – 905 µg/m ³	121.8 ppm 1700 µg/m ³	Yes 2/4	Ventilation Season	(Alves et al., 2016; Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Hänninen et al., 2017; Sá et al., 2017)

Radon	Geogenic (outdoor environment) Soil Mining	29 – 381 Bq/m ³	109 – 952.8 Bq/m ³	Yes 3/6	Floor level Ventilation Number of occupants Building' characteristics (age, construction material) Room location Room Volume Floor type	(Azara et al., 2018; Branco et al., 2016; Curado et al., 2020; Ćurguz et al., 2015; Gulan et al., 2023; Madureira et al., 2016b)
O ₃	Outdoor environment Copy machine	0.002 – 0.08 ppm 4.8 – 37 µg/m ³	3 ppm 15.9 – 31.4 µg/m ³	Not reported	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation Season	(Cabovská et al., 2022; Jovanović et al., 2014; Sá et al., 2017)

293 CO₂= Carbon dioxide; VOC=Volatile Organic Compounds; PM=Particulate Matter; CO=Carbon Monoxide; NO₂=Nitrogen Dioxide; O₃=Ozone

294 **3.3. Homes**

295 This review also focused on homes, due to the potential exposure of all the population
296 groups (infants, children, adults, elderly). The sources and determinants of the presence
297 and concentration of indoor air pollutants described in the Table 2.

298 In the context of homes, studies have identified occupancy as the main source of CO₂
299 (Coggins et al., 2022; Feliciano et al., 2022a; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Foster et al.,
300 2016; Gabriel et al., 2021; Gábor Géczi et al., 2018; Serrano and Licina, 2022; Madureira
301 et al., 2016a; Ramalho et al., 2015), and the number of individuals directly influencing
302 indoor CO₂ concentrations (Brown et al., 2015; Feliciano et al., 2022a; Ferreira and
303 Barros, 2022; Foster et al., 2016; Gabriel et al., 2021; Madureira et al., 2016a).

304 Additionally, it has been recognized that fireplaces (Feliciano et al., 2022a), cooking and
305 combustion processes (Feliciano et al., 2022a; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Serrano and
306 Licina, 2022; Ramalho et al., 2015; Vu et al., 2022) as contribute significantly to indoor
307 CO₂ release, underscoring their impact on indoor air quality. Furthermore, ventilation
308 conditions and the type of ventilation system have been identified as a major determinant
309 of CO₂ concentrations (Alegría-Sala et al., 2022; Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015;
310 Feliciano et al., 2022b; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Foster et al., 2016; Gabriel et al.,
311 2021; Géczi et al., 2018; Serrano and Licina, 2022; Madureira et al., 2015; Madureira et
312 al., 2016a; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Ramalho et al., 2015; Vu et al., 2022), alongside
313 with factors such as house type (Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Ramalho et al., 2015), room
314 volume (Coggins et al., 2022) and building's characteristics (e.g., location, insulation,
315 structure) (Du et al., 2015; Géczi et al., 2018; Madureira et al., 2016a; Ramalho et al.,
316 2015). Seasonal variations and outdoor conditions were also identified as determinants
317 of indoor CO₂ concentrations showing an influence of outdoor air on indoor air
318 characteristics (Alegría-Sala et al., 2022; Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Ramalho et al.,
319 2015).

320 In homes the most relevant indoor sources of VOCs identified were furniture (Coggins et
321 al., 2022; Mečiarová et al., 2017), combustion (Vilčeková et al., 2017), occupancy

322 (Pietrogrande et al., 2021), cleaning products and consumer products (Feliciano et al.,
323 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021; Heeley-Hill et al., 2021; Mečiarová et al., 2017; Ninyà et al.,
324 2022; Pietrogrande et al., 2021). Other sources identified were smoking
325 (Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vilčeková et al., 2017), paints and coatings (Mečiarová et
326 al., 2017), textiles (Coggins et al., 2022), candles (Feliciano et al., 2022a), renovation
327 work (Vilčeková et al., 2017) and construction materials (Mečiarová et al., 2017). Outdoor
328 sources are also major contributors to indoor VOCs levels, especially for benzene,
329 ethylbenzene, xylene, propanal, n-decane and n-dodecane, pentanal, benzaldehyde,
330 and limonene (Kozielska et al., 2020; Villanueva et al., 2015). Ventilation was, by far, the
331 most frequently identified determinant factor as, depending on the frequency and type, it
332 can either help dissipate VOCs produced indoor or allow penetration from outdoor
333 sources (Brown et al., 2015; Coggins et al., 2022; Dallongeville et al., 2016; Du et al.,
334 2015; Feliciano et al., 2022a; Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Madureira et al., 2016a;
335 Mečiarová et al., 2017; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Villanueva et al., 2015). Age of
336 furnishings (Villanueva et al., 2015), number of occupants (Brown et al., 2015), heating
337 systems (Mečiarová et al., 2017; Vilčeková et al., 2017), or frequency of both cleaning
338 and use of cleaning products (Heeley-Hill et al., 2021; Ninyà et al., 2022;
339 Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019) were also recognized as determinant, although in fewer
340 studies. Building location was also a frequently identified as determinant factor, as the
341 outdoor environment is an important source (Villanueva et al., 2015).

342 Regarding formaldehyde, several sources were identified as contributing to indoor
343 concentrations, including furniture and wood-based materials (Birmili et al., 2022;
344 Coggins et al., 2022; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Villanueva et al., 2015), use of candles
345 or incense (Gabriel et al., 2021; Justo Alonso et al., 2022), cooking (Justo Alonso et al.,
346 2022), combustion processes (Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Ramalho et al., 2015), smoking
347 (Villanueva et al., 2015), textiles (Coggins et al., 2022), and paints (Ferreira and Barros,
348 2022). Moreover, as seen before, ventilation type was identified as a determinant of
349 indoor levels of formaldehyde (Brown et al., 2015; Dallongeville et al., 2016; Justo Alonso

350 et al., 2022; Ramalho et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015), as well as building
351 characteristics (e.g., year of construction, location, house type) (Birmili et al., 2022;
352 Brown et al., 2015; Du et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021; Ramalho et al., 2015) and
353 environmental parameters (e.g., temperature and relative humidity) (Brown et al., 2015;
354 Gabriel et al., 2021; Justo Alonso et al., 2022).

355 For NO₂, few studies were available reporting on the sources and determinants of the
356 presence of this pollutant indoors. Nevertheless, two studies reported outdoor sources
357 as the main contributors for indoor NO₂ and, as such, ventilation, insulation, and location
358 of the house were identified as the main determinants that can affect indoor levels
359 (Cibella et al., 2015; Du et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021; Vu et al., 2022). One study also
360 found a significant contribution of indoor sources to indoor concentrations of NO₂,
361 especially cooking activities (Vu et al., 2022).

362 Concerning particulate matter, most of the studies examined the presence of particulate
363 matter sized 2.5 µm and 10 µm. Additionally, four studies quantified the presence of 0.1
364 µm particles (ultrafine particles) (de Gennaro et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021; Madureira
365 et al., 2020; Sajani et al., 2016), while one study identified the presence of 1.0 µm
366 particles (Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019). The main sources identified for indoor levels of
367 PM_{0.1}, PM_{1.0}, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ were cooking and smoking (Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022;
368 Calama-González et al., 2019; Coggins et al., 2022; Custódio et al., 2014; de Gennaro
369 et al., 2015; Du et al., 2015; Faria et al., 2020; Feliciano et al., 2022b; Gabriel et al.,
370 2021; Johnes et al., 2023; Madureira et al., 2020; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Sánchez-
371 Soberón et al., 2019; Scibor, 2019; Siponen et al., 2019; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019;
372 Vilčeková et al., 2017; Vu et al., 2022). Moreover, the outdoor environment and traffic
373 emissions were recognized as contributing factors for PM_{1.0}, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀, alongside
374 with the burning of candles or incense (Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; Faria et al.,
375 2020; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021; Madureira et al., 2016a; Madureira
376 et al., 2020; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Scibor, 2019; Siponen et al., 2019; Zauli Sajani et
377 al., 2016). Other indoor sources of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} include combustion processes

378 (Custódio et al., 2014; de Gennaro et al., 2013; Feliciano et al., 2022a; Serrano and
379 Licina, 2022; Madureira et al., 2016a; Madureira et al., 2020; Maher et al., 2021;
380 Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Siponen et al., 2019; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vu et al.,
381 2022), organic sources such as skin fragments, hair, dandruff, indoor plants and pets
382 (Gabriel et al., 2021; Serrano and Licina, 2022; Madureira et al., 2020; Pietrogrande et
383 al., 2021; Scibor, 2019), as well as resuspension due to human movement (Aquilina and
384 Camilleri, 2022; Brown et al., 2015; Custódio et al., 2014; Madureira et al., 2020;
385 Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019) and cleaning practices such as sweeping (Aquilina and
386 Camilleri, 2022; Faria et al., 2020; Feliciano et al., 2022a; Serrano and Licina, 2022;
387 Madureira et al., 2016a; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019).
388 Ventilation continues to emerge as a critical factor in determining indoor levels of
389 particles of all sizes (Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022; de Gennaro et al., 2013; Du et al.,
390 2015; Feliciano et al., 2022a; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Madureira et al., 2016a;
391 Madureira et al., 2020; Scibor, 2019; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vu et al., 2022).
392 Various determinants of pollutants' presence and concentration related to building
393 characteristics, including building orientation, floor level, location, room volume and
394 house type (apartment, single or multi-family house) were identified (Brown et al., 2015;
395 Du et al., 2015; Faria et al., 2020; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021;
396 Madureira et al., 2020; Ramalho et al., 2015; Scibor, 2019; Siponen et al., 2019;
397 Vilčeková et al., 2017; Zauli Sajani et al., 2016). The heating system also affected
398 particulate matter levels (de Gennaro et al., 2015; Feliciano et al., 2022a; Scibor, 2019;
399 Vilčeková et al., 2017), along with the number of occupants present in the indoor
400 environment (Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Ramalho et al., 2015).

401 As radon is a natural occurring gas that can penetrate into houses, ventilation and
402 insulation are major determinants in indoor concentrations (Antignani et al., 2021; Du et
403 al., 2015; Gábor Géczi et al., 2018; Barry McCarron et al., 2020; McCarron et al., 2019;
404 Vukotic et al., 2019). As it can also penetrate from the ground beneath buildings, the
405 floor level and building foundation were also identified as determinants factors with

406 higher levels on the ground floor (Du et al., 2015). House type also influences radon
407 concentration with single-family houses showing higher levels than apartments (Kropat
408 et al., 2014). This emphasizes the need for buildings to have solid concrete foundations
409 (Kourtidis et al., 2015). Other building' characteristics such as age, location and structure
410 were also identified as determinants factors of indoor radon concentration levels
411 (Bräuner et al., 2013; Kourtidis et al., 2015; Kropat et al., 2014; Mezquita et al.,
412 2019). Thoron, a radioactive isotope of radon, was also identified in a study in Kosovo
413 where geogenic sources and construction materials were identified as sources (Gulan et
414 al., 2014).

415 Finally, fewer studies quantified the presence of other contaminants in homes. For CO,
416 smoking and combustion were the sources identified along with the heating system and
417 ventilation as factors influencing indoor concentrations (Feliciano et al., 2022a; Gabriel
418 et al., 2021). For ozone, outdoor environment was referred as a source, and the use of
419 cleaning products and air freshners were appointed as influencing negatively the ozone
420 concentration due to the release of limonene and α -pinene that react with O₃ (Gabriel et
421 al., 2021). Candle burning was also associated with a 3% increase in home indoor O₃
422 concentration, which was attributed to chance, with no obvious explanation provided
423 (Siponen et al., 2019). One study assessed the presence of black carbon (BC) by
424 identifying cooking, resuspension from cleaning activities such as sweeping and use of
425 candles or incense as sources (Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022). Ventilation and cooking
426 methods were highlighted as important determinants (Aquilina and Camilleri,
427 2022). Regarding PAHs and NPAHs, traffic and combustion processes were the sources
428 of indoor levels identified, and proximity to traffic emerged as a significant determinant,
429 while factors such as ventilation, heating systems and room volume were also
430 considered (de Gennaro et al., 2015; Rutkowski et al., 2019).

431

Table 2 - Sources, concentrations, and determinants of indoor air pollutants presence in homes.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants	References
CO ₂	Occupancy Cooking Fireplace Combustion Smoking	569-2116 ppm	1540-2892 ppm	Yes 2/15 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) House type Season Building' characteristics (structure, insulation, location) Room volume Environmental parameters Other indoor determinants	(Alegria-Sala et al., 2022; Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; Feliciano et al., 2022b; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Foster et al., 2016; Gabriel et al., 2021; Géczi et al., 2018; Serrano and Licina, 2022; Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Madureira et al., 2015; Madureira et al., 2016a; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Ramalho et al., 2015; Vu et al., 2022)
Total VOC	Occupancy Cleaning products Consumer products Smoking Renovations Combustion Furniture Textiles Candles/incense Construction materials Paints/solvents/coatings Organic sources (pets) Cleaning Other indoor sources	50-2610 µg/m ³	604-14690 µg/m ³	Yes 1/11 studies	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Environmental parameters Heating system House type Building' characteristics (age, insulation, location) Mold/dampness Floor type Cleaning products – frequency of use Consumer products – frequency of use Other indoor determinants	(Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; Feliciano et al., 2022b; Gabriel et al., 2021; Heeley-Hill et al., 2021; Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Madureira et al., 2016a; Mečiarová et al., 2017; Ninyà et al., 2022; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vilčeková et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2023; Watts et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2020)
Benzene	Combustion Smoking Outdoor environment Occupancy Other indoor sources	1.1-4.7 µg/m ³	1.3-22.8 µg/m ³	No safe level.	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Building' characteristics (age) Other indoor determinants	(Brown et al., 2015; Dallongeville et al., 2016; Kozielska et al., 2020; Ramalho et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Toluene	Combustion Textiles Construction materials Paints/solvents/coatings Occupancy Other indoor sources	12-25.9 µg/m ³	87.9-398.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Number of occupants Type of ventilation Building' characteristics (age) Other indoor determinants	(Brown et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Ethylbenzene	Combustion Outdoor environment	3.2-3.4 µg/m ³	13-33.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Number of occupants	(Brown et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015)

	Occupancy Other indoor sources				Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Building' characteristics (age, location) Other indoor determinants	
Xylene	Combustion Occupancy Other indoor sources	4.18-5.44 µg/m ³	29.2-30.4 µg/m ³	Not available	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Building' characteristics (location) Other indoor determinants	(Brown et al., 2015)
o-xylene	Outdoor environment Paints/solvents/coatings	0.8-4.4 µg/m ³	3.1-47.1 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (location)	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
Limonene	Outdoor environment	17.1-49 µg/m ³	87.2-278 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (location) Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Pinene	Furniture	6.6-18.5 µg/m ³	54.1-63.1 µg/m ³	Not available	Furniture' characteristics (age) Ventilation Seasonality	(Dallongeville et al., 2016; Heeley-Hill et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Styrene	No sources identified	1.2-2.1 µg/m ³	1.3-6.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (age) Ventilation	(Madureira et al., 2016a; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Acetaldehyde	Smoking Candles/incense Furniture	2.4-23 µg/m ³	2.9-94.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (age, location) Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Other indoor determinants	(Wolfram Birmili et al., 2022; Brown et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021)
Propanal	Outdoor environment Furniture	0.5-5.2 µg/m ³	0.9-23 µg/m ³	Not available	Furniture' characteristics (age)	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
N-decane	Outdoor environment	10.7 µg/m ³	141 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
N-dodecane	Outdoor environment	24.3 µg/m ³	116.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (location)	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
Benzaldehyde	Outdoor environment	0.2-1.8 µg/m ³	0.2-12.1 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (location) Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Acetone	Furniture	50.9 µg/m ³	196 µg/m ³	Not available	Furniture' characteristics (age)	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
Butanal	Furniture Cleaning products	4.5-36 µg/m ³	4.6-88.7 µg/m ³	Not available	Furniture' characteristics (age) Cleaning products – frequency of use	(Nicole Ninyà et al., 2022; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Hexanal	Smoking Furniture Cleaning products	7.9-56.1 µg/m ³	7.9-174.9 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation Furniture' characteristics (age) Cleaning products – frequency of use	(Wolfram Birmili et al., 2022; Ninyà et al., 2022; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Pentanal	Outdoor environment Cleaning products	1.8-16.4 µg/m ³	1.8-45.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation Cleaning products – frequency of use	(Ninyà et al., 2022; Villanueva et al., 2015)

Diethylphthalate	No sources identified	244 ng/m ³	2900 ng/m ³	Not available	Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016)
Diethylhexylphthalate	No sources identified	36 ng/m ³	189 ng/m ³	Not available	Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016)
Diisobutylphthalate	No sources identified	699 ng/m ³	8560 ng/m ³	Not available	Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016)
Dibutylphthalate	No sources identified	102 ng/m ³	527 ng/m ³	Not available	Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016)
Formaldehyde	Occupancy Smoking Furniture Candles/incense Wood stove Cooking Combustion	7.4-54.6 µg/m ³	8.8-86.3 µg/m ³	Yes (1/10 studies)	Number of occupants Ventilation Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) House type Season	(Birmili et al., 2022; Brown et al., 2015; Coggins et al., 2022; Dallongeville et al., 2016; Du et al., 2015; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021; Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Ramalho et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015)
NO ₂	Cooking Outdoor environment	14.2-31.9 µg/m ³	136-147.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation Building' characteristics (location, insulation) Type of ventilation	(Du et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021; Vu et al., 2022)
PM _{0.1}	Cooking Smoking Traffic Outdoor environment Candles/incense Textiles Cleaning	2200-14337 part/cm ³	3544-54083 part/cm ³	Not available	Heating system Ventilation Room volume Building' characteristics (orientation) Cleaning frequency	(de Gennaro et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021; Madureira et al., 2020; Sajani et al., 2016)
PM ₁	Smoking Cooking Resuspension (cleaning activities, human movement) Paint/solvents/coatings	8.1 µg/m ³	134 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Cleaning frequency Number of windows Other indoor determinants	(Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019)
PM _{2.5}	Outdoor environment Traffic Cooking Cleaning Combustion Occupancy Smoking Candles/incense	5-89 µg/m ³	66.7-568 µg/m ³	Yes 9/22 studies	Number of occupants Ventilation Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) House type Building' characteristics (location, orientation, structure, insulation, age) Floor level	(Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022; Brown et al., 2015; Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; Faria et al., 2020; Feliciano et al., 2022a, 2022b; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021; Serrano and Licina, 2022;

	Organic (pets, skin fragments, hair, dandruff) Clothing Resuspension (cleaning activities, human movement) Construction materials Renovations Paints/solvents/coatings				Season Heating system Fuel type Cooking (device, method) Other indoor determinants	Johnes et al., 2023; Madureira et al., 2016a; Madureira et al., 2020; Maher et al., 2021; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Ramalho et al., 2015; Scibor, 2019; Siponen et al., 2019; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vilčeková et al., 2017; Vu et al., 2022; Sajani et al., 2016)
PM ₁₀	Outdoor environment Traffic Cooking Cleaning Combustion Occupancy Smoking Candles/incense Organic sources (pets, plants, skin fragments) Clothing Resuspension (cleaning activities and human movement) Construction materials Renovations	8-74.6 µg/m ³	132.9-722.9 µg/m ³	Yes 5/13 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) House type Building' characteristics (location, orientation, structure, insulation, age) Season Room volume Cooking (device, method) Floor level Type of fuel Humidifier Heating system Other indoor determinants	(Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022; Baloch et al., 2020; Custódio et al., 2014; de Gennaro et al., 2015; Du et al., 2015; Faria et al., 2020; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021; Serrano and Licina, 2022; Madureira et al., 2020; Maher et al., 2021; Ramalho et al., 2015; Scibor, 2019; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vilčeková et al., 2017)
Radon	Geogenic Outdoor environment Soil	27.5-2100 Bq/m ³	149-2321 Bq/m ³	Yes 3/13 studies	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Seepage from the ground Floor level Building's insulation Season Building' characteristics (location, orientation, structure, insulation, age) House type Room volume Other indoor determinants	(Antignani et al., 2021; Bräuner et al., 2013; Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; García-Tobar, 2019; G Géczi et al., 2018; Kourtidis et al., 2015; Kropat et al., 2014; McCarron et al., 2019; McCarron et al., 2020; Mezquita et al., 2019; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Vukotic et al., 2019; Walczak et al., 2020)
CO	Smoking Combustion	0.1-0.6 ppm	1.1-23 ppm	Yes 1/2 studies	Heating system Ventilation	(Feliciano et al., 2022b; Gabriel et al., 2021)
O ₃	Outdoor environment	5.9-6.2 µg/m ³	32-41.3 µg/m ³	Not available	Cleaning products Air freshners	(Siponen et al., 2019)

BC	Cooking Resuspension (cleaning activities) Candle/incense	1 µg/m ³	62.3 µg/m ³	Not available	Cooking method Ventilation	(Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022)
Thoron	Geogenic Construction materials	216 Bq/m ³	406 Bq/m ³	Not available	Season	(Gulan et al., 2014)
PAHs, NPAHs	Traffic Combustion	9.4 µg/g	2.4-51.7 µg/g	Not available	Proximity to traffic Heating system Ventilation Room volume	(de Gennaro et al., 2015; Rutkowski et al., 2019)

433 CO₂= Carbon dioxide; VOC=Volatile Organic Compounds; PM=Particulate Matter; CO=Carbon Monoxide; NO₂=Nitrogen Dioxide; O₃=Ozone; BC= Black Carbon;

434 PAHs=Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon; NPAH=Nitrated polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons

435 **3.4. Lecture halls**

436 Table 3 describes the main sources and determinants of indoor pollutants in lecture halls.
437 Lecture halls are indoor areas, larger than typical classrooms, in universities. Because
438 of their size, the potential exposure of students and staff working in this type of facility
439 can be relevant for a large group of people.
440 As mentioned above, few studies are available for this specific setting. The lecture halls
441 are large rooms that accommodate a high number of people indoors, making the
442 evaluation of indoor air quality very relevant. The sources of indoor air pollutants
443 identified in these studies are like those above mentioned for schools and homes:
444 smoking for formaldehyde (Hu et al., 2022), occupancy for CO₂ (Alegría-Sala et al., 2022;
445 Hu et al., 2022; Ragazzi et al., 2019), geogenic sources for radon (Arias-Ferreiro et al.,
446 2021; Azara et al., 2018; Calvente et al., 2021; Kozak et al., 2013) and the outdoor
447 environment influencing indoor pollution levels (Kovacevic et al., 2015; Majewski et al.,
448 2018, 2016). In terms of determinants, the importance of ventilation stands out, identified
449 in several studies as a factor influencing indoor pollutants levels.

450

451 **Table 3** – Sources, concentrations, and determinants of exposure to indoor air pollution in lecture halls.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants	References
CO ₂	Occupancy	1716 ppm	5000 ppm	Yes 1/3 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural)	(Alegría-Sala et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022; Ragazzi et al., 2019)
Formaldehyde	Smoking	13.3 µg/m ³	Not reported	Yes (National target: 10 µg/m ³)	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural) Room volume	(Hu et al., 2022)
PAHs	Combustion Traffic Outdoor environment	6.8-13.0 ng/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Type of ventilation (mechanical)	(Majewski et al., 2018)
PM ₁	Outdoor environment	9.5-14.5 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not referred	Type of ventilation	(Kovacevic et al., 2015; Majewski et al., 2016)
PM ₁₀	Resuspension	47 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not referred	Type of ventilation	(Kovacevic et al., 2015)
Radon	Geogenic Construction materials Soil	12-1521 Bq/m ³	38-265 Bq/m ³	1/4 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural) Building' characteristics (age) Floor level Seepage from the ground	(Arias-Ferreiro et al., 2021; Azara et al., 2018; Calvente et al., 2021; Kozak et al., 2013)

452 CO₂= Carbon dioxide; PM=Particulate Matter; CO=Carbon Monoxide; PAHs=Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon

453

454 **3.5. Hospitals**

455 Table 4 describes the main sources and determinants of indoor pollutants present in
456 hospitals. It is important to emphasize that in a hospital there are two distinct groups of
457 individuals who are affected by a possible low indoor air quality: the patients (who are
458 occasionally inside the facilities being treated for their health conditions and, therefore,
459 present an inherent vulnerability); and the healthcare professionals (who are exposed in
460 an occupational context and daily). The present study retrieved eight studies in hospitals,
461 thus this setting is likely still understudied. Occupancy was again identified as the main
462 source of CO₂ (Baurès et al., 2020; Loupa et al., 2016; Stamp et al., 2020), PM_{2.5} (Loupa
463 et al., 2016; Scheepers et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020) and total VOCs (Hyttinen et al.,
464 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019; Scheepers et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020), in accordance
465 with the other settings mentioned above. The same authors identified the number of
466 occupants as an important factor influencing the concentration of indoor pollutants (PM_{2.5}
467 and CO₂). For total VOCs, extended assessments were performed in hospitals with
468 measurements and detection of many VOCs. Overall, the concentration of total VOCs in
469 hospitals were below 200 µg/m³, besides some specific situations detailed below.
470 Several sources of VOCs were identified such as occupancy, cleaning products,
471 disinfectants, and pharmaceutical products, and the following factors influenced indoor
472 concentrations and were therefore identified as determinants: ventilation (mechanical),
473 air exchange rate (inverse correlation with indoor concentrations), location in the room,
474 room characteristics (area, volume), furniture (number of pieces). The existence of
475 hospital sparsely decorated rooms combined with an efficient ventilation system are
476 pointed out as an indoor environment with low VOCs levels (Hyttinen et al., 2021). The
477 presence of xylenes was particularly determined in the pathology laboratories, as it is
478 used during samples processing, with the highest concentration determined (3390
479 µg/m³) (Hyttinen et al., 2021). In a broader perspective, for VOCs, the existence of

480 mechanical ventilation was a determinant of indoor air concentrations identified for most
481 compounds.

482 For radon, the presence of this pollutant was assessed in a study conducted in Bari
483 (Italy), and most workplaces (76.1%) reported radon concentrations within the WHO
484 reference value (100 Bq/m³). The higher levels (> 148 Bq/m³) were determined in
485 basement rooms, which means that floor level is a determinant of indoor air radon
486 concentrations (Vimercati et al., 2018).

487

488

Table 4 – Sources, concentrations, and determinants of indoor air pollutants presence in hospitals.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants	References
CO ₂	Occupancy Human activities	451-480 ppm	Not reported	No	Number of occupants Period of the day Ventilation	(Baurès et al., 2020; Loupa et al., 2016; Stamp et al., 2020)
Total VOCs	Occupancy Cleaning products Disinfectants Pharmaceutical products Oxidizing compounds Other indoor sources	33.1- 2449 µg/m ³	170-9287 µg/m ³	No	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate Room characteristics (area, volume) Furniture (number of pieces)	(Hyttinen et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019; Scheepers et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020)
Acetone	Adhesive remover	1-28.4 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	No determinants identified	(Baurès et al., 2020)
Pinene	No sources identified	1.8 µg/m ³	10 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Benzene	No sources identified	1.2 µg/m ³	2.9 µg/m ³	No safe level.	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Benzyl alcohol	Disinfectants	1.2-1.5 µg/m ³	2.3-4.3 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021)
BTEX (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene)	Laboratory reagents Traffic	12.8 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not reported	Ventilation (natural and mechanical) Building structure Thermal insulation Automatized laboratory systems	(Cipolla et al., 2017)
Decamethyl-cyclopentasiloxane	No sources identified	3.9-8.1 µg/m ³	18-140 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Hexamethyl-cyclotrisiloxane	No sources identified	2.3-4.1 µg/m ³	5.1-20 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Octamethyl-cyclotetrasiloxane	No sources identified	1.4-3.6 µg/m ³	5.3-16 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021)
DBP - Dibutyl phthalate	Floor Building materials	30-80 µg/m ³	10-190 µg/m ³	Not available	Season	(Baurès et al., 2020)
DEHP -bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	Floor Building materials	10-30 µg/m ³	30-70 µg/m ³	Not available	Season	(Baurès et al., 2020)
DEP – Diethyl phthalate	Floor Building materials	10-130 µg/m ³	140-260 µg/m ³	Not available	Season	(Baurès et al., 2020)
Decanal	No sources identified	2.7 µg/m ³	7.3 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Dodecane	No sources identified	2.4 µg/m ³	15 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)

Ether	Adhesive remover	6.0-19.3 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	No determinants identified	(Baurès et al., 2020)
Ethanol	Disinfectants	0.5-942.9 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021)
Ethylbenzene	No sources identified	31 µg/m ³	850 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Heptane	No sources identified	1.2 µg/m ³	3.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Hexene	No sources identified	2.6 µg/m ³	11 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Limonene	Cleaning products	0.8-12.3 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Baurès et al., 2020; Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Nonanal	No sources identified	2.2 µg/m ³	6.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Nonane	No sources identified	2.3 µg/m ³	5.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Octane	No sources identified	3.7 µg/m ³	14 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons	No sources identified	6.1 µg/m ³	16 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Phenol	Disinfectants	0.3-0.8 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021)
Toluene	No sources identified	0.8-32.9 µg/m ³	2.5-39 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Baurès et al., 2018; Hyttinen et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019; Scheepers et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020)
TXIB (2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentanediol di-isobutyrate)	No sources identified	0.5-1.7 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Xylene	Laboratory reagents	0.2-110 µg/m ³	0.5-3390 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(144)
1-butanol	Solvents Adhesives Hygiene products Disinfectants	18 µg/m ³	240 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Type of floor	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
2-ethyl-1-hexanol	Disinfectants	1.1 µg/m ³	3 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
2-methyl-1-propanol	Cleaning products Disinfectants	2.3 µg/m ³	5.8 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
2-methyl-2-propanol	Disinfectants	22 µg/m ³	105 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
NO ₂	Traffic	4.9-20.4 µg/m ³	30.2 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Period of the day	(Stamp et al., 2020)

Formaldehyde	Outdoor environment	2.6-21.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	6.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	No	No determinants identified	(Scheepers et al., 2017)
PM _{2.5}	Occupancy Human activities Medical devices Medication Fragrances	1.3-18.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Not reported	No	Ventilation (mechanical and natural) Number of occupants Operation of medical devices	(Loupa et al., 2016; Scheepers et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020)
BC	Outdoor environment	1.0-1.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical and natural) Period of the day	(Loupa et al., 2016)
Radon	Soil	35.8-55.0 Bq/m ³	147.5-538 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	0.9% > 300 q/m3	Ventilation Floor level	(Vimercati et al., 2018)

490

CO₂= Carbon dioxide; VOC=Volatile Organic Compounds; PM=Particulate Matter; CO=Carbon Monoxide; NO₂=Nitrogen Dioxide; O₃=Ozone; BC= Black Carbon

491 **3.6. Other scenarios**

492 This section addresses the results of the scenarios with fewest studies considered
493 eligible for this review: retirement homes (n=5), public transports (n=4) and canteens
494 (n=1). Table 5 describes the main sources and determinants of indoor pollutants. In
495 general, these studies identified few sources and determinants of indoor pollutants. For
496 retirement homes, the studies identified traffic and occupancy, resuspension due to
497 human movements, soil and cleaning products as sources of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. Building
498 location was also a determinant of indoor pollutant concentrations, as facilities near to
499 the airport and the sea, were affected by outdoor sources (Almeida-Silva et al., 2016,
500 2015). Occupancy and number of occupants were also identified in this setting as a
501 source and determinant, respectively (Almeida-Silva et al., 2016, 2015; Almeida et al.,
502 2016; Madureira et al., 2015; Mendes et al., 2016).

503 For public transports, studies were conducted in metro (n=3) and tram (n=1). As
504 expected, occupancy was identified as a source of indoor CO₂ concentrations and the
505 number of people in the carriage as a determinant of these concentrations (Baselga et
506 al., 2022). Regarding PM, occupancy and resuspension were the sources identified for
507 PM₁₀ (Faria et al., 2020; Grydaki et al., 2021), while mechanical wear was identified as
508 the source for PM_{2.5} (Moreno et al., 2015), which leads to train frequency being an
509 important determinant of indoor PM concentrations (Grydaki et al., 2021; Moreno et al.,
510 2015).

511 The study conducted in a university canteen concluded that commercial cooking
512 emissions are an important source of air pollutant gases. Cooking procedures were
513 identified as the main source of VOC, in particular benzene and formaldehyde, with
514 ventilation and the type of cooking device having a strong influence on indoor
515 concentrations (gas or electric stoves representing lower indoor concentrations
516 compared to barbecue grilling)(Alves et al., 2015).

517 **Table 5** – Sources, concentrations, and determinants of exposure to indoor air pollution in retirement homes, transports and canteens.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants	References
Retirement homes						
CO ₂	Occupancy	1033 ppm	2697 ppm	Yes 1/2 studies	Ventilation Number of occupants Season	(Madureira et al., 2015; Mendes et al., 2016)
Total VOC	No sources identified			Yes	Season	(Mendes et al., 2016)
PM _{2.5}	Traffic	63 µg/m ³	952 µg/m ³	Not referred	No determinants identified	(Mendes et al., 2016)
PM ₁₀	Occupancy Resuspension Cleaning products Organic sources (soil) Traffic Sea spray	10.9-29.0 µg/m ³	86-1730 µg/m ³	No	Ventilation (mechanical, natural) Number of occupants Building (location)	(Almeida-Silva et al., 2016, 2015; Almeida et al., 2016)
Transports						
CO ₂	Occupancy	685 ppm	Not reported	No	Ventilation (mechanical, natural) Number of occupants	(Baselga et al., 2022)
PM _{2.5}	Mechanical wear	29-72 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not referred	No determinants identified	(Moreno et al., 2015)
PM ₁₀	Occupancy Resuspension	53-84 µg/m ³	Not reported	Yes 1/2 studies	Frequency of trains	(Faria et al., 2020; Grydaki et al., 2021)
Canteen						
Benzene	Cooking	0.6-2.2 µg/Nm ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Cooking device	(Alves et al., 2015)
Formaldehyde	Cooking	6.5-10.7 µg/Nm ³	Not reported	Not reported	Ventilation (mechanical) Cooking device	(Alves et al., 2015)

518 CO₂= Carbon dioxide; VOC=Volatile Organic Compounds; PM=Particulate Matter

519 **4. Discussion**

520 This review provides a comprehensive overview of indoor air quality in Europe over the
521 last decade. Several scenarios (schools, homes, hospitals, retirement homes, public
522 transport, lecture halls), under consideration in K-HEALTHinAIR project ([www.k-
523 healthinair.eu](http://www.k-healthinair.eu)), were included in the present review with the common characteristic of
524 being scenarios in which individuals spend a large part of their daily lives. An important
525 aspect of indoor air quality is knowing the sources of pollutant emissions of and the
526 factors that influence their presence indoors, the determinants. A deep knowledge on
527 these two aspects will allow better solutions to be deployed to improve indoor air quality.
528 As mentioned by Settimo et al (2020), several guidelines, orientations and regulations
529 have been published by several entities aiming to improve the indoor air quality;
530 nevertheless, there is no harmonized regulation in the European region that defines limits
531 for indoor air pollutants similar to those of the Air Quality Directive available for outdoor
532 air, despite being recognized as an important determinant of health (Settimo et al., 2020).
533 The research conducted in the last decade and reviewed in the present manuscript
534 highlights another important aspect, i.e., the reduced number of studies that performed
535 a detailed and robust statistical analysis to identify the sources and the determinants of
536 the presence of indoor air pollutants. The present review considered as eligible studies
537 that did not perform a statistical analysis to attribute a specific source to each pollutant
538 but relied on previous knowledge to make this attribution. Nevertheless, 33% of studies
539 in schools, 45% of studies in homes, and 38% of studies in hospitals, performed a
540 statistical analysis to establish an association between sources and pollutants and to
541 identify the determinants of indoor concentrations. Statistical methods varied from
542 inferential tests such as Mann-Whitney, Kruskal-Wallis, to more complex analysis using
543 Principal Component Analysis, linear mixed effects and multivariate regression models.
544 On the one hand, these characteristics emphasize the need to conduct detailed data
545 collection in indoor environments, which then allows to perform a robust and complex
546 analyse and draw conclusions with enough strong weight of evidence. On the other hand,

547 these results allowed us to recognize the complexity of this field, the difficulty in collecting
548 accurate, reliable and useful data on indoor air quality, including contextual data, and
549 this may partially explain the absence of a harmonized legislation in larger geographic
550 areas, such as, Europe.

551 As part of this review, it was possible to identify the sources and determinants of indoor
552 pollutants for several scenarios. Regarding CO₂, occupancy was a common source
553 across all scenarios, with further contribution of cooking, smoking, and fireplaces
554 (combustion) in homes. Ventilation and the number of occupants were the main
555 determinants identified as influencing the indoor CO₂ concentrations. It has been
556 recognized before that the control of CO₂ indoors is a challenge, despite the installation
557 of ventilation systems (López et al., 2023). Regarding PM, occupancy, resuspension,
558 human activities (cleaning, cooking, craft, use of chalk), organic sources (pets, molds,
559 soil), clothes, construction materials and traffic, were identified as sources of exposure.
560 The number of occupants, the ventilation, and the characteristics of buildings (especially
561 in what regards construction materials) played an important role for the levels of PM
562 indoors. This identification is fundamental for the implementation of preventive measures
563 to reduce human exposure in indoor settings, since PM are deleterious for health,
564 especially the smaller sizes that can be inhaled and absorbed (Bo et al., 2017; Zhang et
565 al., 2021). The installation of air conditioners with high-performance filter systems
566 together with air purifiers to neutralize fine dust should be considered, especially if the
567 outdoor air is strongly affected by traffic-intensive roads, airports or industrial areas
568 (Pulimeno et al., 2020).

569 Regarding VOCs, cleaning activities, craft activities, disinfectants and furniture were
570 identified as sources of indoors VOC (e.g., formaldehyde, limonene, pinene). In
571 hospitals, some laboratories were identified as hotspots, related to the use of xylene and
572 formaldehyde, similar to more recent findings in this setting (Riveron et al., 2023).

573 In terms of measures to prevent the presence of these pollutants indoors, we could
574 consider the Hierarchy of Controls approach described in some EU regulations dedicated

575 to Occupational Hygiene issues (European Commission, 2004). This approach provides
576 a framework for determining ways to implement systems or controls (from most effective
577 to least effective) to prevent/control exposure, starting with the elimination or substitution
578 by a less hazardous process or toxic substances. In the case of indoor air quality, our
579 goal is to prevent the presence of the indoors pollutants and, if not elimination is not
580 possible, to reduce (control) their presence. One option could also be a combination of
581 these two actions, i.e., prevention and reduction. Preventive actions could be either on
582 the regulatory or the technical level. For the former, a good example is the restrictions
583 established in the EU under the scope of Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and
584 Restriction of Chemicals (1907/2006/ECD – REACH) that limits the presence of
585 substances, such as formaldehyde, in certain construction products and materials (e.g.
586 furniture that contains wood or other materials used indoors) (European Commission,
587 2023). At a technical level, we can refer to correct thermal insulation of building with a
588 good isolation of the materials used in the construction process. In both cases we aim to
589 eliminate the presence of indoor pollutant.

590 In the case of reduction (or control) we can point to measures such as an effective
591 ventilation and the selection of low-emission products starting from building materials to
592 furniture, other household or office equipment and cleaning products. In combination with
593 these, we can also put in place administrative controls such as limiting the number of
594 occupants in each indoor space and/or providing guidance on how/when to use the
595 natural/mechanical ventilation or even defining strict schedules for developing cleaning
596 procedures and listing the cleaning products allowed to be used.

597 All these actions should be chosen based on specific aspects of the indoor settings. For
598 instance, schools and hospitals imply higher risks due to higher vulnerability of certain
599 groups of occupants and users or are more prone to the presence of specific pollutants
600 (e.g. VOCs in schools and hospitals), although with different sources of exposure.

601 Relevant is the fact that some of the measures already implemented in the EU, mainly
602 those related with regulatory actions, need to be evaluated to allow concluding on

603 effectiveness or need for revision, and future research projects should tackle this need
604 (Dimitroulopoulou et al., 2023).

605 Although this review comprised several indoor scenarios and the most recent period of
606 10 years, thus giving an updated perspective of this field, some limitations should be
607 mentioned. The time frame and the geographic region (Europe) as criteria left out of the
608 scope of this review studies conducted before 2013 and in other countries (e.g., United
609 States of America, Australia, Japan, China). Several studies did not conduct a statistical
610 analysis to attribute the source of indoor pollutants and to analyse the determinants,
611 relying on available literature and previous knowledge.

612

613 **5. Conclusions**

614 Within this review it was possible to identify the most important emission sources and
615 determinants of the presence of indoor pollutants in settings where people spend most
616 of their time. In schools, the main indoor sources of indoor pollutants were determined
617 to be the occupants, cleaning products, wood materials and electronic equipment, and
618 school activities (use of chalk, textiles, physical activity), with the outdoor sources being
619 also important contributors for the presence of pollutants indoors. The ventilation
620 systems and the number of occupants (e.g., students) in the rooms were the main factors
621 determining the presence of indoor pollutants. The results obtained for lecture halls are
622 aligned with the ones obtained for schools regarding the sources and determinants of
623 exposure. In homes, the main sources of indoor pollutants were related with activities
624 such as the cooking, cleaning and burning candles and/or incenses, as well as organic
625 sources such as pets, hairs, molds. The type of heating system plays also an important
626 role, with combustion systems contributing more for the presence of indoor pollutants.
627 Similarly to the findings in schools, the ventilation and the number of residents were the
628 main factors determining the presence of indoor pollutants. Results obtained for
629 retirement homes and canteens are aligned with the ones found for homes. In hospitals,
630 the main sources were occupancy, human activities, disinfectants, laboratory reagents

631 and floor, while the ventilation and number of occupants were again determinant for the
632 concentration of indoor pollutants. For public transports, occupancy was an important
633 source as well as aspects related to the infrastructure (e.g., mechanical ware in trains
634 and subway). The present review made also possible to discuss some of the actions that
635 are already in place or should be implemented in the future to prevent and control the
636 presence of pollutants indoors, and mostly importantly to recognize some of the research
637 gaps that need to be addressed in future or ongoing research projects.

638

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667 **Declaration of competing interest**

668 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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677 **Data availability**

678 Data will be made available on request.

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1 **Table 1** – Sources, concentrations, and determinants of indoor air pollutants presence in schools.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources of exposure	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants of exposure	References
CO ₂	Occupancy Outdoor air	410 – 3780 ppm	1000-4434 ppm	Yes 11/26 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Room volume Season Building maintenance Classroom orientation Physical activities Other indoor pollutants	(Alves et al., 2016; Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2014; Hänninen et al., 2017; Jovanović et al., 2014; Kaewrat et al., 2021; Lazovic et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016; Madureira, Paciência, Rufo, Severo, et al., 2016; Mečiarová et al., 2018; Muhič & Muhič, 2022; Rufo et al., 2016; Sá et al., 2017; Schibuola & Tambani, 2020; Stabile et al., 2016; Turanjanin et al., 2014; Ukéhaxhaj et al., 2023; Villanueva et al., 2021; Vornanen-Winqvist, Järvi, et al., 2018; Vornanen-Winqvist, Salonen, et al., 2018)
Total VOC	Cleaning products Floor material Class materials (art & crafts, textiles) Consumer products	19-1543 µg/m ³	84-820.2 µg/m ³	No	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Season Room volume Type of floor	(Alves et al., 2016; Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Fromme et al., 2013; Jovanović et al., 2014; Madureira et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016c; Mečiarová et al., 2018; Ninyà et al., 2022; Sá et al., 2017)
Benzene	Outdoor environment Floor material Class materials (textiles)	0.44 – 5.24 µg/m ³	0.6 – 20.1 µg/m ³	Not reported	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation	(Brdarić et al., 2019; de Gennaro et al., 2013; Fromme et al., 2013; Madureira et al., 2016; Marzocca et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021; Ukéhaxhaj et al., 2023)
Limonene	Cleaning products Whiteboard Class activities Class materials (textiles) Other indoor sources	3.08 – 26.6 µg/m ³	3.6 – 249 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical)	(de Gennaro et al., 2013; Fromme et al., 2013; Marzocca et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020; Szabados et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2018)
Pinene	Cleaning products Class materials (textiles) Class activities	4.85 – 55.6 µg/m ³	9.9 – 73 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical)	(de Gennaro et al., 2013; Fromme et al., 2013; Stamp

	Other indoor sources					et al., 2020; Szabados et al., 2021)
Toluene	Outdoor environment Class materials (art & crafts, textiles) Other indoor sources	1.5 – 25 µg/m ³	1.9 – 202.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical)	(Fromme et al., 2013; Madureira et al., 2016; Marzocca et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021)
Naphtalene Tetrachloroethylene Trichloroethylene	Class materials (textiles)	0.5 – 2.18 µg/m ³ 0.09 – 4.4 µg/m ³ 0.19 – 0.45 µg/m ³	1 – 6.05 µg/m ³ 0.6 – 67.1 µg/m ³ NR	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical)	(Fromme et al., 2013)
Ethylbenzene Styrene Xylenes	Outdoor environment Class materials (art & crafts) Cleaning products	0.76 – 1.64 µg/m ³ 0.44 – 1.75 µg/m ³ 5.37 µg/m ³	1.4 – 9.14 µg/m ³ 0.43 – 4.2 µg/m ³ 34.6 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(Marzocca et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021)
Acetaldehyde Hexanal Propionaldehyde	Other indoor sources	5.28 – 9.31 µg/m ³ 9.17 – 15.8 µg/m ³ 1.49 µg/m ³	11 µg/m ³ 26.9 – 32.7 µg/m ³ 6.54 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(Szabados et al., 2021)
Decane	Furniture	NR	5.86 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(de Gennaro et al., 2013)
2-butoxyethanol	Cleaning products	31.5 µg/m ³	46.4 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(Marzocca et al., 2017)
Formaldehyde	Furniture (wood-based) Organic sources (dampness, mold) Electronics Class activities Smoking Traffic Class materials (textiles) Other indoor sources	0.01 – 102 µg/m ³	12.9 – 126.9 µg/m ³	Yes 1/7 studies	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Building' characteristics (location, age) Type of floor	(Brdarić et al., 2019; Blanka Cabovská et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022; Jovanović et al., 2014; Sá et al., 2017; Szabados et al., 2021; Ukéhaxhaj et al., 2023)
NO ₂	Outdoor environment Traffic Wall material Heating/combustion	4.89 – 31 µg/m ³	13.7 – 69 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation Number of occupants Floor level Building' characteristics (location, age)	(Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2015; Hu et al., 2022; Szabados et al., 2021; Ukéhaxhaj et al., 2023; Villanueva et al., 2018)
PM _{0.1}	Outdoor environment Traffic Resuspension Other indoor sources Chalk Cooking	2445-19241 part/cm ³	3985-185000 part/cm ³	Not reported	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Number of occupants Building' characteristics (location) Type of board	(Cavaleiro Rufo et al., 2016; Paunescu et al., 2017; Reche et al., 2014; Rivas et al., 2014; Klara Slezakova et al., 2019; Villanueva et al., 2021)

	Wood Other indoor sources				Floor level Type of floor Building with kitchen Room volume Time (period of day)	
PM _{1.0}	Chalk Traffic Occupancy Outdoor environment	2.4 – 70.1 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not reported	Building location Ventilation Number of occupants	(Pacitto et al., 2018; Polednik, 2013; Sá et al., 2017)
PM _{2.5}	Occupancy Chalk Outdoor air Resuspension (cleaning activities and movements of students) Traffic Soil Construction material Class materials (art & crafts, textiles) Organic sources (dampness, mold)	1.27 – 117 µg/m ³	27.1 – 279 µg/m ³	Yes 6/18 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation Building' characteristics (location) Type of playground Season Construction material Floor level Window's material	(Alves et al., 2016; Amato et al., 2014; Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2015; Di Gilio et al., 2017; Faria et al., 2020; Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Jovanović et al., 2014; Kovacevic et al., 2015; Pacitto et al., 2018; Polednik, 2013; Rivas et al., 2015, 2014; Sá et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020; Tofful and Perrino, 2015; Villanueva et al., 2021; Vormanen-Winqvist et al., 2018a)
PM ₁₀	Occupancy Chalk Resuspension (cleaning activities and movements of students) Outdoor air Soil Other indoor sources Organic sources (dampness, mold) Construction material Craft activities Traffic	14 – 388 µg/m ³	20 – 490 µg/m ³	Yes 7/21 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation Building' characteristics (location) Class activities Floor level Season Footwear (shoes/socks)	(Almeida et al., 2016; Alves et al., 2016; Bamparesos et al., 2020; Cabovská et al., 2022; Chatzidiakou et al., 2014; Faria et al., 2020; Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Fischer et al., 2015; Fromme et al., 2013; Jovanović et al., 2014; Kovacevic et al., 2015; Leppänen et al., 2020; Madureira et al., 2016; Madureira et al., 2016c; Pacitto et al., 2018; Pallarés et al., 2021; Polednik, 2013; Sá et al., 2017; Schibuola and Tambani, 2020; Szabados et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2021)
CO	Outdoor environment Smoking Combustion	0.42 – 9.1 ppm 0.48 – 905 µg/m ³	121.8 ppm 1700 µg/m ³	Yes 2/4	Ventilation Season	(Alves et al., 2016; Ferreira and Cardoso, 2014; Hänninen et al., 2017; Sá et al., 2017)

Radon	Geogenic (outdoor environment) Soil Mining	29 – 381 Bq/m ³	109 – 952.8 Bq/m ³	Yes 3/6	Floor level Ventilation Number of occupants Building' characteristics (age, construction material) Room location Room Volume Floor type	(Azara et al., 2018; Branco et al., 2016; Curado et al., 2020; Ćurguz et al., 2015; Gulan et al., 2023; Madureira et al., 2016b)
O ₃	Outdoor environment Copy machine	0.002 – 0.08 ppm 4.8 – 37 µg/m ³	3 ppm 15.9 – 31.4 µg/m ³	Not reported	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Classroom orientation Season	(Cabovská et al., 2022; Jovanović et al., 2014; Sá et al., 2017)

CO₂= Carbon dioxide; VOC=Volatile Organic Compounds; PM=Particulate Matter; CO=Carbon Monoxide; NO₂=Nitrogen Dioxide; O₃=Ozone

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Table 2 - Sources, concentrations, and determinants of indoor air pollutants presence in homes.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants	References
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CO ₂	Occupancy Cooking Fireplace Combustion Smoking	569-2116 ppm	1540-2892 ppm	Yes 2/15 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) House type Season Building' characteristics (structure, insulation, location) Room volume Environmental parameters Other indoor determinants	(Alegría-Sala et al., 2022; Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; Feliciano et al., 2022b; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Foster et al., 2016; Gabriel et al., 2021; Géczi et al., 2018; Serrano and Licina, 2022; Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Madureira et al., 2015; Madureira et al., 2016a; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Ramalho et al., 2015; Vu et al., 2022)
Total VOC	Occupancy Cleaning products Consumer products Smoking Renovations Combustion Furniture Textiles Candles/incense Construction materials Paints/solvents/coatings Organic sources (pets) Cleaning Other indoor sources	50-2610 µg/m ³	604-14690 µg/m ³	Yes 1/11 studies	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Environmental parameters Heating system House type Building' characteristics (age, insulation, location) Mold/dampness Floor type Cleaning products – frequency of use Consumer products – frequency of use Other indoor determinants	(Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; Feliciano et al., 2022b; Gabriel et al., 2021; Heeley-Hill et al., 2021; Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Madureira et al., 2016a; Mečiarová et al., 2017; Ninyà et al., 2022; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vilčeková et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2023; Watts et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2020)
Benzene	Combustion Smoking Outdoor environment Occupancy Other indoor sources	1.1-4.7 µg/m ³	1.3-22.8 µg/m ³	No safe level.	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Building' characteristics (age) Other indoor determinants	(Brown et al., 2015; Dallongeville et al., 2016; Kozielska et al., 2020; Ramalho et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Toluene	Combustion Textiles Construction materials Paints/solvents/coatings Occupancy Other indoor sources	12-25.9 µg/m ³	87.9-398.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Number of occupants Type of ventilation Building' characteristics (age) Other indoor determinants	(Brown et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Ethylbenzene	Combustion Outdoor environment Occupancy Other indoor sources	3.2-3.4 µg/m ³	13-33.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Building' characteristics (age, location) Other indoor determinants	(Brown et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Xylene	Combustion Occupancy	4.18-5.44 µg/m ³	29.2-30.4 µg/m ³	Not available	Number of occupants	(Brown et al., 2015)

	Other indoor sources				Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Building' characteristics (location) Other indoor determinants	
o-xylene	Outdoor environment Paints/solvents/coatings	0.8-4.4 µg/m ³	3.1-47.1 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (location)	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
Limonene	Outdoor environment	17.1-49 µg/m ³	87.2-278 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (location) Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Pinene	Furniture	6.6-18.5 µg/m ³	54.1-63.1 µg/m ³	Not available	Furniture' characteristics (age) Ventilation Seasonality	(Dallongeville et al., 2016; Heeley-Hill et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Styrene	No sources identified	1.2-2.1 µg/m ³	1.3-6.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (age) Ventilation	(Madureira et al., 2016a; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Acetaldehyde	Smoking Candles/incense Furniture	2.4-23 µg/m ³	2.9-94.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (age, location) Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Other indoor determinants	(Wolfram Birmili et al., 2022; Brown et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021)
Propanal	Outdoor environment Furniture	0.5-5.2 µg/m ³	0.9-23 µg/m ³	Not available	Furniture' characteristics (age)	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
N-decane	Outdoor environment	10.7 µg/m ³	141 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
N-dodecane	Outdoor environment	24.3 µg/m ³	116.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (location)	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
Benzaldehyde	Outdoor environment	0.2-1.8 µg/m ³	0.2-12.1 µg/m ³	Not available	Building' characteristics (location) Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Acetone	Furniture	50.9 µg/m ³	196 µg/m ³	Not available	Furniture' characteristics (age)	(Villanueva et al., 2015)
Butanal	Furniture Cleaning products	4.5-36 µg/m ³	4.6-88.7 µg/m ³	Not available	Furniture' characteristics (age) Cleaning products – frequency of use	(Nicole Ninyà et al., 2022; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Hexanal	Smoking Furniture Cleaning products	7.9-56.1 µg/m ³	7.9-174.9 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation Furniture' characteristics (age) Cleaning products – frequency of use	(Wolfram Birmili et al., 2022; Ninyà et al., 2022; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Pentanal	Outdoor environment Cleaning products	1.8-16.4 µg/m ³	1.8-45.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation Cleaning products – frequency of use	(Ninyà et al., 2022; Villanueva et al., 2015)
Diethylphthalate	No sources identified	244 ng/m ³	2900 ng/m ³	Not available	Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016)
Diethylhexylphthalate	No sources identified	36 ng/m ³	189 ng/m ³	Not available	Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016)

Diisobutylphthalate	No sources identified	699 ng/m ³	8560 ng/m ³	Not available	Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016)
Dibutylphthalate	No sources identified	102 ng/m ³	527 ng/m ³	Not available	Ventilation	(Dallongeville et al., 2016)
Formaldehyde	Occupancy Smoking Furniture Candles/incense Wood stove Cooking Combustion	7.4-54.6 µg/m ³	8.8-86.3 µg/m ³	Yes (1/10 studies)	Number of occupants Ventilation Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) House type Season	(Birmili et al., 2022; Brown et al., 2015; Coggins et al., 2022; Dallongeville et al., 2016; Du et al., 2015; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021; Justo Alonso et al., 2022; Ramalho et al., 2015; Villanueva et al., 2015)
NO ₂	Cooking Outdoor environment	14.2-31.9 µg/m ³	136-147.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation Building' characteristics (location, insulation) Type of ventilation	(Du et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021; Vu et al., 2022)
PM _{0.1}	Cooking Smoking Traffic Outdoor environment Candles/incense Textiles Cleaning	2200-14337 part/cm ³	3544-54083 part/cm ³	Not available	Heating system Ventilation Room volume Building' characteristics (orientation) Cleaning frequency	(de Gennaro et al., 2015; Gabriel et al., 2021; Madureira et al., 2020; Sajani et al., 2016)
PM ₁	Smoking Cooking Resuspension (cleaning activities, human movement) Paint/solvents/coatings	8.1 µg/m ³	134 µg/m ³	Not available	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Cleaning frequency Number of windows Other indoor determinants	(Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019)
PM _{2.5}	Outdoor environment Traffic Cooking Cleaning Combustion Occupancy Smoking Candles/incense Organic (pets, skin fragments, hair, dandruff) Clothing	5-89 µg/m ³	66.7-568 µg/m ³	Yes 9/22 studies	Number of occupants Ventilation Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) House type Building' characteristics (location, orientation, structure, insulation, age) Floor level Season Heating system Fuel type Cooking (device, method) Other indoor determinants	(Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022; Brown et al., 2015; Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; Faria et al., 2020; Feliciano et al., 2022a, 2022b; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021; Serrano and Licina, 2022; Johnes et al., 2023; Madureira et al., 2016a; Madureira et al., 2020; Maher et al., 2021; Pietrogrande et al., 2021;

	Resuspension (cleaning activities, human movement) Construction materials Renovations Paints/solvents/coatings					Ramalho et al., 2015; Scibor, 2019; Siponen et al., 2019; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vilčeková et al., 2017; Vu et al., 2022; Sajani et al., 2016)
PM ₁₀	Outdoor environment Traffic Cooking Cleaning Combustion Occupancy Smoking Candles/incense Organic sources (pets, plants, skin fragments) Clothing Resuspension (cleaning activities and human movement) Construction materials Renovations	8-74.6 µg/m ³	132.9-722.9 µg/m ³	Yes 5/13 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) House type Building' characteristics (location, orientation, structure, insulation, age) Season Room volume Cooking (device, method) Floor level Type of fuel Humidifier Heating system Other indoor determinants	(Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022; Baloch et al., 2020; Custódio et al., 2014; de Gennaro et al., 2015; Du et al., 2015; Faria et al., 2020; Ferreira and Barros, 2022; Gabriel et al., 2021; Serrano and Licina, 2022; Madureira et al., 2020; Maher et al., 2021; Ramalho et al., 2015; Scibor, 2019; Stamatelopoulou et al., 2019; Vilčeková et al., 2017)
Radon	Geogenic Outdoor environment Soil	27.5-2100 Bq/m ³	149-2321 Bq/m ³	Yes 3/13 studies	Type of ventilation (natural, mechanical) Seepage from the ground Floor level Building's insulation Season Building' characteristics (location, orientation, structure, insulation, age) House type Room volume Other indoor determinants	(Antignani et al., 2021; Bräuner et al., 2013; Coggins et al., 2022; Du et al., 2015; García-Tobar, 2019; G Géczí et al., 2018; Kourtidis et al., 2015; Kropat et al., 2014; McCarron et al., 2019; McCarron et al., 2020; Mezquita et al., 2019; Pietrogrande et al., 2021; Vukotic et al., 2019; Walczak et al., 2020)
CO	Smoking Combustion	0.1-0.6 ppm	1.1-23 ppm	Yes 1/2 studies	Heating system Ventilation	(Feliciano et al., 2022b; Gabriel et al., 2021)
O ₃	Outdoor environment	5.9-6.2 µg/m ³	32-41.3 µg/m ³	Not available	Cleaning products Air freshners	(Siponen et al., 2019)
BC	Cooking Resuspension (cleaning activities) Candle/incense	1 µg/m ³	62.3 µg/m ³	Not available	Cooking method Ventilation	(Aquilina and Camilleri, 2022)

Thoron	Geogenic Construction materials	216 Bq/m ³	406 Bq/m ³	Not available	Season	(Gulan et al., 2014)
PAHs, NPAHs	Traffic Combustion	9.4 µg/g	2.4-51.7 µg/g	Not available	Proximity to traffic Heating system Ventilation Room volume	(de Gennaro et al., 2015; Rutkowski et al., 2019)

17 CO₂= Carbon dioxide; VOC=Volatile Organic Compounds; PM=Particulate Matter; CO=Carbon Monoxide; NO₂=Nitrogen Dioxide; O₃=Ozone; BC= Black Carbon;

18 PAHs=Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon; NPAH=Nitrated polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons

19 **Table 3** – Sources, concentrations, and determinants of exposure to indoor air pollution in lecture halls.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants	References
CO ₂	Occupancy	1716 ppm	5000 ppm	Yes 1/3 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural)	(Alegría-Sala et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022; Ragazzi et al., 2019)
Formaldehyde	Smoking	13.3 µg/m ³	Not reported	Yes (National target: 10 µg/m ³)	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural) Room volume	(Hu et al., 2022)
PAHs	Combustion Traffic Outdoor environment	6.8-13.0 ng/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Type of ventilation (mechanical)	(Majewski et al., 2018)
PM ₁	Outdoor environment	9.5-14.5 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not referred	Type of ventilation	(Kovacevic et al., 2015; Majewski et al., 2016)
PM ₁₀	Resuspension	47 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not referred	Type of ventilation	(Kovacevic et al., 2015)
Radon	Geogenic Construction materials Soil	12-1521 Bq/m ³	38-265 Bq/m ³	1/4 studies	Number of occupants Type of ventilation (natural) Building' characteristics (age) Floor level Seepage from the ground	(Arias-Ferreiro et al., 2021; Azara et al., 2018; Calvente et al., 2021; Kozak et al., 2013)

20 CO₂= Carbon dioxide; PM=Particulate Matter; CO=Carbon Monoxide; PAHs=Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon

21 **Table 4** – Sources, concentrations, and determinants of indoor air pollutants presence in hospitals.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants	References
CO ₂	Occupancy Human activities	451-480 ppm	Not reported	No	Number of occupants Period of the day Ventilation	(Baurès et al., 2020; Loupa et al., 2016; Stamp et al., 2020)
Total VOCs	Occupancy Cleaning products Disinfectants Pharmaceutical products Oxidizing compounds Other indoor sources	33.1- 2449 µg/m ³	170-9287 µg/m ³	No	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate Room characteristics (area, volume) Furniture (number of pieces)	(Hyttinen et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019; Scheepers et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020)
Acetone	Adhesive remover	1-28.4 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	No determinants identified	(Baurès et al., 2020)
Pinene	No sources identified	1.8 µg/m ³	10 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Benzene	No sources identified	1.2 µg/m ³	2.9 µg/m ³	No safe level.	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Benzyl alcohol	Disinfectants	1.2-1.5 µg/m ³	2.3-4.3 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021)
BTEX (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene)	Laboratory reagents Traffic	12.8 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not reported	Ventilation (natural and mechanical) Building structure Thermal insulation Automatized laboratory systems	(Cipolla et al., 2017)
Decamethyl-cyclopentasiloxane	No sources identified	3.9-8.1 µg/m ³	18-140 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Hexamethyl-cyclotrisiloxane	No sources identified	2.3-4.1 µg/m ³	5.1-20 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Octamethyl-cyclotetrasiloxane	No sources identified	1.4-3.6 µg/m ³	5.3-16 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021)
DBP - Dibutyl phthalate	Floor Building materials	30-80 µg/m ³	10-190 µg/m ³	Not available	Season	(Baurès et al., 2020)
DEHP -bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	Floor Building materials	10-30 µg/m ³	30-70 µg/m ³	Not available	Season	(Baurès et al., 2020)
DEP – Diethyl phthalate	Floor Building materials	10-130 µg/m ³	140-260 µg/m ³	Not available	Season	(Baurès et al., 2020)
Decanal	No sources identified	2.7 µg/m ³	7.3 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Dodecane	No sources identified	2.4 µg/m ³	15 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)

Ether	Adhesive remover	6.0-19.3 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	No determinants identified	(Baurès et al., 2020)
Ethanol	Disinfectants	0.5-942.9 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021)
Ethylbenzene	No sources identified	31 µg/m ³	850 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Heptane	No sources identified	1.2 µg/m ³	3.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Hexene	No sources identified	2.6 µg/m ³	11 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Limonene	Cleaning products	0.8-12.3 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Baurès et al., 2020; Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Nonanal	No sources identified	2.2 µg/m ³	6.6 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Nonane	No sources identified	2.3 µg/m ³	5.5 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Octane	No sources identified	3.7 µg/m ³	14 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons	No sources identified	6.1 µg/m ³	16 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Phenol	Disinfectants	0.3-0.8 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Air exchange rate	(Hyttinen et al., 2021)
Toluene	No sources identified	0.8-32.9 µg/m ³	2.5-39 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Baurès et al., 2018; Hyttinen et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2019; Scheepers et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020)
TXIB (2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentanediol di-isobutyrate)	No sources identified	0.5-1.7 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
Xylene	Laboratory reagents	0.2-110 µg/m ³	0.5-3390 µg/m ³	Not available	No determinants identified	(144)
1-butanol	Solvents Adhesives Hygiene products Disinfectants	18 µg/m ³	240 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Type of floor	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
2-ethyl-1-hexanol	Disinfectants	1.1 µg/m ³	3 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
2-methyl-1-propanol	Cleaning products Disinfectants	2.3 µg/m ³	5.8 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
2-methyl-2-propanol	Disinfectants	22 µg/m ³	105 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical)	(Rautiainen et al., 2019)
NO ₂	Traffic	4.9-20.4 µg/m ³	30.2 µg/m ³	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Period of the day	(Stamp et al., 2020)

Formaldehyde	Outdoor environment	2.6-21.7 µg/m ³	6.3 µg/m ³	No	No determinants identified	(Scheepers et al., 2017)
PM _{2.5}	Occupancy Human activities Medical devices Medication Fragrances	1.3-18.6 µg/m ³	Not reported	No	Ventilation (mechanical and natural) Number of occupants Operation of medical devices	(Loupa et al., 2016; Scheepers et al., 2017; Stamp et al., 2020)
BC	Outdoor environment	1.0-1.2 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical and natural) Period of the day	(Loupa et al., 2016)
Radon	Soil	35.8-55.0 Bq/m ³	147.5-538 µg/m ³	0.9% > 300 q/m3	Ventilation Floor level	(Vimercati et al., 2018)

22

CO₂= Carbon dioxide; VOC=Volatile Organic Compounds; PM=Particulate Matter; CO=Carbon Monoxide; NO₂=Nitrogen Dioxide; O₃=Ozone; BC= Black Carbon

23 **Table 5** – Sources, concentrations, and determinants of exposure to indoor air pollution in retirement homes, transports and canteens.

Indoor air pollutant	Sources	Concentration (range of means)	Concentration (range of maximums)	Exceedance of national legislation	Determinants	References
Retirement homes						
CO ₂	Occupancy	1033 ppm	2697 ppm	Yes 1/2 studies	Ventilation Number of occupants Season	(Madureira et al., 2015; Mendes et al., 2016)
Total VOC	No sources identified			Yes	Season	(Mendes et al., 2016)
PM _{2.5}	Traffic	63 µg/m ³	952 µg/m ³	Not referred	No determinants identified	(Mendes et al., 2016)
PM ₁₀	Occupancy Resuspension Cleaning products Organic sources (soil) Traffic Sea spray	10.9-29.0 µg/m ³	86-1730 µg/m ³	No	Ventilation (mechanical, natural) Number of occupants Building (location)	(Almeida-Silva et al., 2016, 2015; Almeida et al., 2016)
Transports						
CO ₂	Occupancy	685 ppm	Not reported	No	Ventilation (mechanical, natural) Number of occupants	(Baselga et al., 2022)
PM _{2.5}	Mechanical wear	29-72 µg/m ³	Not reported	Not referred	No determinants identified	(Moreno et al., 2015)
PM ₁₀	Occupancy Resuspension	53-84 µg/m ³	Not reported	Yes 1/2 studies	Frequency of trains	(Faria et al., 2020; Grydaki et al., 2021)
Canteen						
Benzene	Cooking	0.6-2.2 µg/Nm ³	Not reported	Not available	Ventilation (mechanical) Cooking device	(Alves et al., 2015)
Formaldehyde	Cooking	6.5-10.7 µg/Nm ³	Not reported	Not reported	Ventilation (mechanical) Cooking device	(Alves et al., 2015)

24 CO₂= Carbon dioxide; VOC=Volatile Organic Compounds; PM=Particulate Matter

Figure 1 - Decision tree for stage I screening (a) and stage II screening (b).

Figure 2 - Workflow and results for stage I and stage II of the systematic literature review.

Figure 3 - Scenarios studied in the scientific literature eligible for data extraction.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: